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Latest updates on novel Covid-19 virus Outbreak and Its Genomic Characterization

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The main source of Covid-19 pandemic is Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARSCoV-2); belongs to beta-coronavirus genus and first case of coronavirus was revealed in Wuhan city of China in 2019. In severe cases there is high occurrence of multiple organ dysfunctions, elevated d-dimer levels, oxygen saturation rate is less than 94. SARS COV2 genome consisting of M(Membrane), N(Nucleocapsid), S(Spike), ORF (Open Reading Frame) and E(Envelope) genes that encodes the structural proteins like M, N, S and E gene. Open reading frame (ORF) are largely non-structural accessory proteins in genes. M gene is an integral membrane protein that are responsible for the virus's shapes, encourage membrane curvature and involve in the attachment to the envelope proteins like E, S, and HE as well as with the nucleocapsid or in the formation of intracellular virus without the involvement of S protein. N gene encodes nucleocapsid protein which is structural protein responsible for various cell activities, replication and transcription, used for diagnostic purposes on the basis of primer and probe sequencing. Whereas, S gene is responsible for pathogenesis, producing host immune response by their antigenic property and neutralizing antibodies to protect from infectivity.

In this review we summarized background, clinical symptoms, pathological features and genetic characteristics of SARS-CoV-2. Previously known coronavirus intermediate host was cat and giraffe whereas SARS-CoV-2 host is currently unknown. We recapitulate the current knowledge of structural and non-structural genes of coronavirus. On the surface of S gene there is a receptor called ACE2 (Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2) where virus binds and entered into the cell. We also discuss the vaccines that are used to reduce mortality and morbidity rate of viral infection. But the duration of immunity induced by vaccine is still unknown

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INTRODUCTION

In past years, there were many lethal diseases that were spread in many places like swine flu, Ebola virus, chickenpox and nipah virus etc. But now the new strain of virus infects people and mammals, indicated as Coronavirus (Alam and Qamar., 2020). Corona Virus is an enveloped positive-sense RNA, and further classified as alpha (α), beta (β), gamma (γ) and delta (δ)

corona virus and present novel coronavirus belongs to beta-coronavirus genus (Phan., 2020; Corman et al. 2020).

During the past 1000 years the novel coronavirus has been repeatedly involved in causing infection (Yosra et al. 2020). The coronavirus had been found mostly in domestic and wild mammals and birds that are natural reservoirs of current novel virus whereas all

human CoVs as zoonotic origin. But bats seem to be the natural host of all the coronaviruses till now.

Figure 1: Structure of coronavirus, this could be the new form of COVID-19 (Mostafa et al .2020).

In 1960, the many cases of coronaviruses had been reported that was called MERS-CoV (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome) and 5 new coronaviruses cases were reported that leads to fatality in 2003 (Helmy et al .2020; Jeffrey et al 2005). SARS and MERS, the two strains were similar to each other in many ways that caused fatal illness, pathogenesis and mortality rate in older patients of age above 60 was 11%(Masood et al .2020).Incubation period of virus is 124 hours (5 days) and case-fertility rate is 2.3%. Homology modelling described both 2019-nCoV and SARS-CoV, had a similar receptor-binding domain, whereas amino acid showed variation at some residues when bind to the Angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) in humans (Jin et al .2020). The first case of corona virus in Wuhan city of China was reported in 2019, was originated from bat, pigs and mammals and transmitted from person to person by direct and indirect contact with droplets or contaminated fomites (Fong et al. 2021). On 20th January 2020, WHO confirmed more cases in the travellers of many countries like in Wuhan, Thailand, Japan and in Korea (Corman et al. 2020).

The extreme side effects and death rate of SARS-CoV2 are increased in numbers, most particularly from the widespread epidemic regions of China. The time period between 22nd to 25th of January Chinese National Health Commission deals with the serious conditions of health crisis and declare the details regarding the early 17 deaths that further raise the numbers to 56 deaths

(Rothana et al. 2021; Bauddha and Husain., 2021). Spike protein of COVID-19 attached to the ACE2 (the angiotensin converting enzyme) receptor and allows virus to enter and infect cells, the genome replication and transcription process of COVID-19 starts in the cytoplasmic membrane when the virus enter into the host cells (Vanaerschot et al. 2020). SARS-CoV-2 is widely spread through direct contact, airborne droplet and clinically had a triphasic pattern of disease. Most probably the patients at first phase of SARS with sore throat, a non-productive cough, fever, and myalgia. During the second phase of the sickness, dyspnea and hypoxia, with constantly fever and frequently accompanied by loose feces. In fact, replication of the virus is thought to occur in upper respiratory tract of mucosal epithelium (nasal cavity and pharynx), with more increase in the lower respiratory tract (Jin et al. 2020). Patients bowels become more raised. A few patients' respiratory status proceeded to fall apart and they created intense respiratory distress syndrome often requiring mechanical breath at the third week and the intensity of the disease was connected with increasing age, with mortality coming to 50% for patients over 60 (Weiss and Leibowitz., 2011).

The long-suffering individuals since of the contagious infection of COVID-19 shown a much higher leukocyte numbers, related with the abnormal respiration, moreover an increase within the levels of D-dimer, plasma pro-inflammatory cytokines and rate of erythrocyte sedimentation rate was closely studied. Reports and analysis of coronavirus cases showed a patient suffering with fever for 5 days, most importantly the body temperature of 39, cough and breathing problems, if collected samples of sputum gave positive real time PCR results that also confirm COVID-19 is infectious disease (Bauddha and Husain., 2021).

In Pakistan, first case of coronavirus was reported in Karachi and Islamabad on the same day that originally came from Iran on January 26, 2020 (Mahmood et al. 2021). The number of COVID19 cases expanded quickly in Pakistan within 2 months, coming to the 16,473 cases till the end of April month. Such quick progress of Coronavirus cases in Pakistan required a viable activity plan by complete shutdown of all educational institute, indoor, outdoor gathering and must figure out how to control the emergence of coronavirus (Abid et al. 2020). In Pakistan the fourth wave of coronavirus, delta variant had been facing in July which was first diagnosed in India and now it has become the globally dominant

variant.

Figure 2: The life cycle of coronavirus. Replication cycle starts when virion attached by its S protein to the host cell receptors, through the S1 subunit. That cause fusion between virus envelope and cellular membrane (Haan and Rottier., 2005).

The genomic classification of the novel Coronavirus from Wuhan city by collecting various study groups from Broncho alveolar lavage fluid and cultured isolates samples was based on NGS (Next Generation Sequencing). Covid-19 cases were further classified into acute, moderate and chronic symptoms observed in positive cases like temperature, dry cough, headache, weakness, anosmia and difficult breathing. In chronic cases there is high occurrence of multiple organ dysfunction, high FDP's levels, oxygen saturation rate is less than 94%, fibrinogen and prolonged thrombin time. Patient with chronic infection in the ICU shows elevated levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines that played an important role in disease severity. Different clinical manifestations based on chest X-rays; physician referred this disease as pneumonia induced by coronavirus (Junejoa et al. 2020). Biological sample can be used for testing of COVID-19 patient like sputum, nasopharyngeal swabs, anal swabs, blood, and feces for nucleic acid detection. Sample taken from nasopharyngeal swabs are mostly preferred for real-time fluorescence RT-PCR detection of CoV-2019. (Kumar et al. 2020; Yuki et al 2020)

Figure 3: Genes of CoV. 5' UTR; E, M, N, S, ORF 1a and 1b (rep gene);

and accessory genes; 3' UTR are all structural genes of Coronavirus. Accessory genes of all Coronavirus species SARS-CoV, SAR-CoV2 and MERS-CoV different from each other. SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV, both having many similarities; however, differences in genetic material indicated by green bold boxes (Asrani et al. 2020).

Initially passive immunization was involved in the administration of antibodies from a cured patient after exposure to a non-exposed individual, though vaccines were the most efficient method of preventing and controlling the pandemics. To make a new vaccine against the coronavirus, it is important to understand the immune response (Dai and Gao., 2021). Four main viral structural proteins N, S, E and M are tested for development of vaccine against SARS and MERS. These protein antigens can be delivered as the viral vector vaccine or DNA recombinant vaccine to induce immune responses (Ong et al. 2020). 1/3 S the spike protein is the main because the RBD is an attractive vaccine target. N protein is a representative antigen for the T-cell response so nucleocapsid-based vaccine was also purposed for SARS (Oliveira et al. 2020). The first human clinical trial of a COVID-19 vaccine commenced on 1st week of March 2020, in the United States. Now, CoV-2 vaccine is present but the time period of immunity induced by vaccine is still unknown.

The inactive SARS-CoV-2 vaccine Betapropiolactone, developed mainly in China with good immune responses and immune efficacy, increases SARS-CoV-2 specific IgG antibodies that reduce the replication of the virus in the lung tissue, throat and nasal cavity. Wuhan Institute of Biological Products developed vaccines that are Sinopharm and Sinovac and the authorized vaccine in Pakistan are Sinovac, Sinopharm, Pfizer and Moderna. Moderna/NIAID

and BioNTech/Pfizer prevents COVID-19 cases with more than 90% efficacy by their mRNA vaccines whereas United Kingdom have approved Pfizer. There was considerable scientific evidence that vaccines reduced mortality and morbidity rates (Perveen et al. 2021).

SARS-CoV2 has large single strand RNA genome ranging from 27-31 kilo bites (kb) with approximately 80–160 nm diameter, G- C (Guanine-Cytosine) contents varies 32% to 43% (Lai., 2021). Among all the RNA virus, it has the largest genome because there are 29891 nucleotides, that encodes 9860 amino acids, and contains 3' UTR at one side and 5' UTR and 14 open reading frames regions at other side of structural gene N (Masood et al. 2020). The 5'terminus of CoV gene consists of two open reading frames (ORFs): ORF 1a and ORF 1b, covering two thirds of the genome length (Lai., 2021). ORF 1a and ORF 1ab can be converted to two polyproteins (pp), pp1a and pp1ab, and synthesized into 16 non-structural proteins (Nsps) involved in the viral genome. In all coronavirus, genes that encodes major structural proteins occurred in the 5-30 sequence as in the Envelope (E), Membrane(M), Nucleocapsid(N) and Spike(S) [28]. These sequence variation of amino acid is 7%, 8 %, 9% and 10% in the E, M, N and S Region respectively. Four major structural proteins encode by CoV genome at 3'-terminus that has 342 bp and 5' untranslated region has 265 bp. Envelope of coronavirus is formed by E, M and S proteins, meanwhile capsid is formed to pack the viral genome by N protein. The one of the most important genes of coronavirus is the S gene, this small membrane enveloped protein(3831bp) helps in entry of virus into host cell (Masood et al. 2020).

We extract RNA for Whole-genome sequencing (WGS), helps in understanding of the virus's origin, evolution and to trace infection spreading route. All of its genetic sequences were uploaded to the Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data (GISAID) platform on January 10, 2020, Complete genetic sequence analysis provides useful information of infection by tracking gene transmission through the genome. The most important technique of sequencing was Nano pore sequencing of amplicon libraries which was obtained by the method of multiplex PCR. Once the sequence is completed, bioinformatics analysis is used to combines the whole data in kilo base(kb) range, helped in the detection of viral genomes without the whole procedure of PCR (Zhang and Holmes., 2020). For further

studies of mutations in SARS CoV-2 there will be deep sequencing molecular methods such as metagenomics next- generation sequencing and next-generation sequencing but are currently unable to detect COVID-19. The primary host of SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV for animals are the civet and camel for humans before transmission (Junejoa et al. 2020). In novel virus the mutation rate is low during the viral replication cycle, nsp 14 protein on both single-stranded and double-stranded RNA acts as 3'- 5'exoribonuclease. Risk of mutations have been arisen due to immunological pressure by virus in infected patients with mild then with serious disease. The virus may have over mutated due to circumvent response from human immune system [Dai and Gao., 2021; Nguyen et al. 2021]. In general, the random mutations have no meaningful changes on virus ability to cause or transmit disease whereas some can cause mutations have impact on lethality, transmissibility or infectivity. In United Kingdom (UK), Another new variant VUI-202012/01 is identified through mutation in virus genomic sequencing having 17 mutations in virus genetic code that alter the virus shape. There are 4 types of mutation that are synonymous, nonsynonymous, insertion and deletion, are detected. All these mutations that occur so far are obtain from mutation pattern analysis (Nguyen et al. 2021). In S protein, these variants have 1 deletion, 2 insertions, 14 non coding alleles 46 missenses and 52 synonymous (Jin et al. 2020). Even though for continue tracking of SARS-CoV-2 evolution, it is important to execute multiple vaccines and therapeutics in a given human population (Chen et al. 2021).

Open reading frame (ORF) gene

The whole RNA genome is present as the template for protein translation that encoded in two open reading frames encode protein (Asadullah et al. 2020). Open reading frame (ORF) are non-structural accessory proteins in an alphanumeric set but the order is not accurate. in genes. There is a diverse set of ORFs with alphanumeric designations, but not in the correct order. Two main gene clusters are encoded in ORF protein, the first gene cluster is the orf3 region, S and E genes have greater emphasis was placed, second gene cluster is between M and N genes. Different reading frames are part of the nucleocapsid N gene (Barik., 2021). At 5'end two open reading frames ORF1a/b encoding the coronavirus replicase. The replicas polyproteins pp1a and pp1ab.Pb1ab

encoding non-structural proteins with size of 30119bp (7078), 29844bp (7096aa) and 29751bp (7073aa). (35). ORFs are involved in viral transcription and replication. The starting codon of ORF is ATG with a length of 70 base pairs (bp). In coronaviruses, two-thirds of the 3'end include orf1a and orf1b genes which generate the viral RdRP that contain coding regions for PP1a and PP1b, separated by a stop codon. The polyprotein processed into ~16 non-structural proteins (called 'NSPs') that are essential for forming replicase transcriptase complex. During the viral life cycle NAPs of SARSCoV2 include cysteine 3C-like proteinase (NSP5), papain-like protease (NSP3), the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (NSP12), and helicase/triphosphatase (NSP13), have enzymatic functions. (36). At the 3'end four main structural proteins S, E, M, N are encoded by ORFs 10, 11 on the one-third of the genome. Eight accessory structural proteins from ORF 3(a/b), p6, 7(a/b), 8b, 9b, to orf14. Overall, the number, location, and identity of the ORFs are variable between the various genera and individual viruses ORFs expression as well as function. remain largely unknown because the identity, number, and location is variable in different genera., and thus, they are currently designated by numbers 3a to 9c. ORFs have been studied in model coronaviruses but SARS-CoV-2 encodes the largest accessory protein with 274 to 27 aa long on ORF 3a and ORF 3b the shortest accessory protein (Barik., 2021). ORF3a is present in pathogenesis because of expressing Spike protein on the cell surface. The + 1 reading frame of ORF3a is overlapped by the coding sequence of ORF3b. In host cell key protein ORF 3b, 6 and N inhibit the expression of IFN regulatory factor 3 (IRF-3) and IFN- β (Zhang and Holmes., 2020). ORF8 play role in adaptation to the human host following interspecies transmission, gene consists of 366 nucleotides, situated between M and N gene. ORF 8a protein is absent in 2019nCoV. Whereas 8b protein has 84 amino acids in SARS-CoV but in novel virus 121 amino acids that is much longer (Asadullah et al. 2020). ORF8b is involved in the cytokine cascade and induces NLRP3 inflammasome in macrophages that have intensive SARS-CoV infection. Macrophages or monocytes are infected; virus infects lungs epithelial cells. The sequence of ORF8 encodes a secreted protein with an alpha structure and beta sheets consisting of six strands. The current genome of the present novel virus makes difference from other due to the analysis done on the overlapping of 7bORFs, 9b,

and 9c ORFs (Mousavizadeh and Sorayya., 2021). The ORFs 9b and 9c accessory genes overlapped the last structural protein encoded by nucleocapsid. OFRs 9c is known to be the shortest gene with 70 aa whereas the 9b is translated by the mechanism of ribosomal scanning. In SARS-CoV-2 the ORF 10 is expressed only during infection and code 38 aa long peptide (Mousavizadeh and Sorayya., 2021).

Membrane (M) gene

Envelope Corona virus with RNA genome contains structural genes, one of them is M gene called integral membrane protein or encoding membrane protein of gene. M protein is glycosylated hydrophobic protein with three transmembrane segments present on N- or O-glycosylation location at the end of Nucleocapsid. M protein fluctuates two layers of membrane, NH₂- terminal space clearing out the infection outside and a long COOH end (cytoplasmic space) inside the virion. M gene is 221–230 amino acid residues in length, but for the 1 group of M proteins have around 30 residues amino terminus longer. In CoV, Gene qualities of the major structural proteins happen within 5'–3' arrange as E, S, N and M (Neuman et al. 2011; Mousavizadeh and Sorayya., 2021). Corona viruses' group 1 and 3 have M protein with N-glycosylated sugar and group 2 coronavirus, M protein are Glycosylated. M protein with N- or O-linked sugar, viruses that contains N sugars that bring elevated level of interferon's other than O-linked sugars' proteins with N-linked or Olinked sugars, viruses that contains N sugars that bring elevated level of interferon's other than Olinked sugars (Haan and Rottier., 2005). M obtains high-mannose N-glycan's that are along these lines altered in golgi to complex N glycan. N-glycosylation profile and non-appearance of Glycosylation on M protein relates to SARS-CoV. Glycosylation of M protein is unable to do virus assembly, oligosaccharides engaged the host-virus interconnection (Neuman et al. 2011). M protein is essential in virus shapes, encourages membrane curvature and involve in the attachment to the envelope proteins like E, S, and HE as well as with the nucleocapsid, so that it involves in the synthesis of virus intracellularly with exception of S protein (Mousavizadeh and Sorayya., 2021). S protein, N protein and genomic RNA of several virions analysis indicate that each of them help to regulate virion size and variability, possibly through M. Enlarged M protein is affiliated with stiffness, clusters of spikes and a

relatively précised membrane curvature. M genes are less likely to mutate than other genes and mutations in SARS-CoV-2 genes may be helpful in explaining the possible pathogenicity, infection, and transmission relationship between human host and SARSCoV-2. Their interactions affected directly or indirectly by several point mutations and variability in mutations in SARS-CoV-2 may enhance the emergence of the virus in rapid transmission (Kim et al. 2020). Immunofluorescence examination appears as S is detected in some locations alongside the secretory pathway from the endoplasmic reticulum to the plasma layer where M mostly localized within Golgi apparatus, where it accumulates and trades in vesicles (Neuman et al. 2020).

NUCLEOCAPSID(N) GENE

The N gene that encodes the N (Nucleocapsid) protein in SARS CoV2, is the most common in infected cells contains 377–455 amino acids of mass 45 to 60 kDa (Haan and Rottier., 2005). Nucleocapsid is structural protein that plays an important role in various cell activities, in transcription and in virion assembly by the help of other proteins (McBride et al. 2014). The N gene is more resistant as compare to the S gene because of 90% amino acids content less mutant over time. In the serum of infected patient's immunoglobulin G (IgG) is used as diagnostic agent. N protein is antigen that shows the immune response by producing the T cells, IgG antibodies and cytotoxic activities (Dutta et al. 2020). The N protein had three fragments that were separate to each other by splitters, two acidic domains were likely involved in protein– protein interactions and central domain served as the RNA-binding domain. The N protein of coronavirus is a 46-kDa, 422 amino acids phosphoprotein that contains 20–30% sequence of N protein and its C-terminus forms a dimer, building block of nucleocapsid. The major role of N protein is in packaging the whole viral genome into a ribonucleoprotein (RNP) particle which protects the genomic RNA by the strong bond and allows it to be incorporated into a viable virion helps in the replication and transcription (Chang et al. 2014). N protein has the strong bond with nucleic acids through electrostatic interactions and in vitro studies have shown that it binds to single stranded RNA (ssRNA), single stranded DNA (ssDNA), double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) and the N protein antibodies inhibited viral RNA synthesis by 90%. coronavirus. The N protein has similarity in structure with viral RNA and helps in viral

transcription (Batra et al. 2021). N protein shows the relationship between a variety of host cell proteins, including chemokine Cxcl16, Smad3, pyruvate kinase, B23 phosphoprotein and translation elongation factor-1 alpha (Zhang et al. 2010). For the diagnostic purposes, N protein based on primer and probe sequences, for the identification of the disease, showed slight changes in gene sequence, referred as genetically steady protein and therapeutic target in antiviral therapy (Hung et al. 2012; Kao et al. 2010; Wang et al. 2020). The N gene has been proposed as a potential primer and probe target region and detected 63 symptomatic and 119 asymptomatic mutations, G204R, R203K and P214L, had elevated peaks in the G.2 clade (Kim et al. 2020). ORF1b have recently been found, which is affected by two commercial assays in target genes detection. Both mutations are of the Cytosine-Thymine type, linked with the host cells mRNA editing mechanism by the SNP (single nucleotide polymorphism) while other is Guanine-Uracil mutation based on the sensitivity for the detection of N gene (Vanaerschot et al. 2020).

SPIKE(S) GENE

The S gene of coronavirus is surrounded by a crown like structure called S protein. There are metalloprotease cell surfaces (human aminopeptidase N) present in the various cells of intestines, lungs, kidney and on macrophages that serves as a receptor of coronavirus. The S gene encodes a surface protein1, the spike protein, which is a homotrimeric glycoprotein complex responsible for pathogenesis. S glycoprotein is composed on the surface of the rough endoplasmic reticulum of precursor of 1273 amino acid glycoprotein. The size of spike protein is 180 - 200kDa which is made up of S1 domain (16 to 560 aa), carboxy-terminal cysteine cluster 15 amino acid signal sequence while S1 domain contains the receptor binding domain and N-terminal domain. The RBD (Receptor Binding Domain) binds to host cell ACE2 receptor (Walls et al.2020; Perveen et al. 2021). On ACE2 receptors there is aminopeptidase N region and it is composed of transmembrane glycoprotein which is expressed on respiratory, enteric tracts and immune system epithelial cells. Whereas the receptor binding domain is highly mutable region. These mutations in RBD leads to increase the interactions with Human angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), encourage the synthesis of endosomes and activate the viral fusion activity (Huang et al. 2020; Wang et al. 2020). S2 domain

is composed of short cytoplasmic tail domain amino acids 1139 to 1173. These two domains: S1 helps in attachment of virion to host cell by receptors, whereas S2 involved in the post-fusion of membrane for the entry of the cell by the process called TMPRSS2 as an enzyme called protease (Mousavizadeh and Sorayya., 2021; Kirchdoerfer et al. 2016). It is mostly recognized by its structural protein present on its surface called peplomers consisting of dimer or trimer of S proteins (Raabe et al. 1990).

For the entry of cell, there is a receptor ACE2 called membrane protein of type 1 in SARS CoV-2, mostly present in the lung, heart, kidney associated with the cardiovascular diseases. ACE 2 is composed of N terminal peptidase domain (PD), C terminal Collectrin-like domain (CLD), which ends with 40 residues intracellular segment and a single transmembrane helix. Pathogenesis of COV-2, there is a cleavage of angiotensin (Ang) I to Ang-(1-9), whereas ACE 2 helps in direct binding to S protein by providing a site. The S protein helps the ACE 2 receptor for binding ten times more than the SARS CoV helps in the pathogenesis of COVID 19 (Jin et al. 2020). On the surface of SARS- COV2, there is a transmembrane protein called neuropilin that helps for the attachment to the virus and infects the disease in host cells. Neuropilins are the steady molecules that are attached to the surface of the host cells and also involved in many cellular activities like repulsion, survival (Vinod., 2021). The S protein encoding by S gene, which is structural protein develops immunity of host by their antigenic property. In order to protect from the infectivity, S protein is targeted and produce the neutralizing antibodies(nAbs) that are IgG and IgM by stop their entry into host cells (Hoffmann et al. 2020). It is also used for the diagnostic purposes due to its antigen and for making of vaccine. Other proteins are also used for the vaccines but S protein is being expressed on DNA and RNA vector (Vinod., 2021). Further, the S protein is used as essential tool in antigen detection for the development of vaccine and test procedures. The antibodies of S proteins, circulating T follicular helper (TFH) cells and memory B cells are used as vaccine shots for clinical trials in coronavirus infection (Nikhra et al. 2021).

Envelope (E) gene

The E gene is a short, essential membrane protein in which no variation has been detected. The CoV envelope having three basic proteins,

M(membrane), E(Envelope), and S (Spike), embedded in the membrane. Assembly and budding of coronavirus are accomplished by both M and E protein (DeDiego et al. 2007). The E protein is present as a transmembrane protein in virions in low copy number and having a 21- to 29-amino-acid hydrophobic region, short (7 to 9 amino acid) hydrophilic amino terminus region, followed by a hydrophilic carboxyl terminus (Corse and Machamer., 2002). Coronavirus E proteins function as ion channels, forming at least one amphipathic alpha-helix by having hydrophobic domain and in membranes assumed ion-conductive pore formed by oligomerization (Torres et al. 2006). Only a small fragment of E protein is integrated into the virion envelope and while other remains within the infected cell during the replication cycle (Venkatagopalan et al. 2015). There have been reduced viral titers, yield incompetent progeny or crippled viral development without the presence of E protein in coronavirus, that shows the importance of E protein in maturation and production of virus. cycle (Malik., 2020). A considerable segment of the transmembrane domain (TMD) consisting of two non-ionic, neutral amino acids, leucine as well as valine, providing a strong hydrophobicity to the E protein, that was revealed by the comparative and phylogenetic analysis of SARS-CoV E (Wu et al. 2003). Binding motif of CoV E protein also known as the postsynaptic density protein 95 (PSD95)/ zonula occludens-1 protein (zo-1) (PDZ)-binding motif (PBM) /Drosophila disc large tumor suppressor (Dlg1), important for viral infection and involved in SARS-COV-E pathogenesis (Javier et al. 2011). M and E proteins interaction between the cytoplasmic tails drives VLP (virus like particles) production indicated that E protein participates in viral assembly (Lim et al. 2001).

Vaccinated animal models were protected against infective challenges and developed both cellular and humoral strong immune responses, indicates that CoV vaccines can potentially be used for prophylactic treatment, with mutated or deficient E, yet the span of resistance does not seem to have been established yet (Schoeman and Fielding. 2019).

CONCLUSION

Analyzing the Covid -19 novel virus genome including its four main structural genes for understanding the virus and how the pandemic can be controlled. In this review, we firstly discuss the difference between the previously discovered

genera of beta coronavirus and the recent novel virus. Furthermore, SARS-CoV, MERS, and SARS-CoV-2 all are originated from the bat whereas the intermediate host of SARS-CoV-2 is still unknown. SARS-CoV-2 has the capability to transfer from one person to another through direct or indirect contact. Therefore in this way, the virus spread from one another as a result of the pandemic spread all over the world including Pakistan. The pandemic has been involved in disturbing the economy as well as the normal lifestyle use of masks and social distancing was compulsory everywhere. In addition, ORF 10 encode amino acids this protein is only expressed during SARS-CoV-2 infection and the Spike protein expressed ACE2 receptor that allows entry and release of the virus. E gene is the only gene in which no variation has been detected. Various point mutations of SARS-CoV-2 have been observed in these four structural genes. Currently, no proper treatment has been available whereas some vaccines are been introduced but the duration of immunity induced by the vaccine is unknown.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared that present study was performed in absence of any conflict of interest.

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